

Crop and resource management

Fertilizer management

Integrated N management in irrigated lowland rice

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Using both organic and inorganic fertilizers is a way to save on costs and to maintain soil health, resulting in sustained crop production. We conducted a field experiment at Cuttack from 1988 to 1992 in an alluvial (Inceptisol) sandy loam soil with pH 6.0, 0.5% organic C, 0.058% total N, 36 ppm available P, and 1 meq exchangeable k/100 g soil.

The treatments (see table) combined inorganic fertilizer (prilled urea [PU]) in equal proportion (50:50) with organic fertilizers: farmyard manure (FYM), *Azolla* compost, water hyacinth compost, and green manures (*Sesbania aculeata* and *S. rostrata*). A conventional 3-way split application of PU, urea supergranule (USG) placement 7 d after transplanting (DT), and a no-N control were used for comparison. The N rate was maintained at 75 kg/ha.

Treatments were replicated four times in a randomized block design. The photoperiod-sensitive, long-duration variety Gayatari (CR1018) was planted in the first fortnight of July, at a spacing of 15 × 15 cm. Green manure crops were incorporated into the field at 40 d.

N content, on a dry-weight basis, was 1.9% for *S. aculeata*, 1.6% for *Azolla* compost, 1.5% for *S. rostrata*, 1.3% for FYM, and 1.2% for water hyacinth compost.

Grain yield in different integrated N application schedules was comparable with that of the conventional 3-way split application of PU and USG treatments during the first 4 yr of the study (see table). During the fifth year, grain yield was significantly lower in the 3-way split of PU compared with the other treatments. Yield declined over time in all the

Influences of different integrated N management treatments on grain yield of rice. Cuttack, India. 1988-92.

Treatment ^a	Grain yield (t/ha)				
	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992
Control (no N)	4.1	4.0 (2.4) ^b	3.8 (8.5)	3.8 (7.3)	3.3 (19.2)
FYM + PU (50:50)	6.2	5.7 (8.3)	5.4 (12.8)	5.7 (7.0)	5.3 (13.3)
<i>Azolla</i> compost + PU (50:50)	6.2	5.6 (10.6)	5.4 (13.8)	5.9 (5.5)	5.2 (15.9)
Water hyacinth compost + PU (50:50)	6.3	5.3 (10.9)	5.4 (13.4)	5.7 (9.4)	5.3 (14.6)
<i>S. aculeata</i> + PU (50:50)	6.4	5.6 (11.9)	5.4 (15.5)	5.6 (11.5)	5.2 (17.7)
<i>S. rostrata</i> + PU (50:50)	6.3	5.7 (10.4)	5.4 (15.4)	5.9 (7.3)	5.2 (17.1)
Conventional 3-split application of PU	6.3	5.4 (10.4)	5.4 (14.6)	5.5 (13.8)	4.7 (25.8)
USG at 7 DT	6.2	5.5 (12.0)	5.3 ^c (15.3)	5.8 (7.7)	5.2 (17.0)
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.3	0.5	0.3 ^c	0.5	0.4

^a N application treatments = 75 kg N/ha. ^b Figures in parentheses indicate yield decline from the first year.

treatments. The decline was, in general, greater in the conventional 3-way split of PU than in the integrated N application schedules and USG treatment in all years except 1990, when it was similar across treatments.

Organic and inorganic fertilizer applied in equal proportions can be used to realize higher and sustained yields in irrigated lowland rice. ■

Evaluating *Sesbania* and urea supergranules vs prilled urea in rice and their residual effect on the succeeding wheat crop

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Much interest exists in ways to exploit renewable N sources that sustain soil fertility in rice cropping. Rice - wheat sequence is an important cropping system in the tarai Mollisol of U.P. We investigated how timing applications of urea supergranules (USG) in combination with green manure (GM) (*Sesbania aculeata* grown in situ)—compared with best split applications of prilled urea (PU)—affect yield and N uptake of the rice crop.

The succeeding wheat crop yield and N uptake, nitrate production at wheat planting, and available soil N at the end

of the experiment were recorded.

The clay loam soil had pH 7.3, 1.35% (0-20 cm depth) and 0.5% (20-50 cm depth) organic C, 0.12% total N, and 200 m mol (+)/kg cation exchange capacity. Zinc (5 kg ZnSO₄ + 2.5 kg lime in 1000 liters of water/ha) was sprayed on the rice crop at 60 and 90 d after transplanting (DT) to control Zn deficiency. Ammonium N of the wet soil was determined by modified Nessler method (Jackson 1973). At wheat planting, nitrate N was determined by chromotropic acid method (Sims and Jackson 1974). Available soil N was determined by alkaline potassium permanganate method (Black 1973). *Sesbania* was raised in situ using 50 kg seeds/ha and was irrigated once before sowing and once during the growing season in all 3 yr. Average fresh weight of *Sesbania* was 34.1 kg/ha in 1987-88, 32.9 kg/ha in 1988-89, and 31.7 kg/ha in 1989-90.

Integrated management of *Sesbania* GM + 29 kg N/ha as USG applied 2-5 wk

Table 1. Grain yield and N uptake (grain + straw) of rice crop. ^a Pantnagar, U. P., India. 1987-90.

Treatment ^b	Grain yield (t/ha)			N uptake (kg/ha)		
	1987-88	1988-89	1989-90	1987-88	1988-89	1989-90
Control	3.9 a	2.9	2.7	56.4 a	49.8	47.8
PU @ 40 kg N	4.0 a	3.8	3.8	78.9 b	76.8 a	81.4 a
PU @ 80 kg N	5.3 bc	5.0 a	5.0 a	94.1 c	95.8 abc	97.3 ab
PU @ 120 kg N	5.8 cd	5.9 b	6.1 b	103.7 cd	111.7 bcd	107.5 ab
S + USG 1 WT	5.2 b	5.0 a	4.9 a	70.4 ab	89.5 ab	91.3 ab
S + USG 2 WT	6.4	6.0 b	6.5 b	124.8 e	111.7 bcd	118.1 b
S + USG 3 WT	5.8 cd	5.9 ab	6.3 b	97.8 cd	121.5 cd	109.5 b
S + USG 4 WT	5.9 d	6.0 b	6.2 b	111.4 de	129.5 d	117.5 b
S + USG 5 WT	6.0 d	5.7 b	5.9 b	110.1 de	97.3 ab	103.1 ab
CD at 5%	0.50	0.59	0.71	15.0	26.7	27.1
<i>r</i> to panicle number	0.893**	0.918**	0.943**	-	-	-
<i>r</i> to wet soil ammonium N						
15 DT	-	0.702*	0.626	-	0.666*	0.666*
30 DT	-	0.702*	0.888**	-	0.662	0.879**
45 DT	-	0.807**	0.853**	-	0.838**	0.823**
60 DT	-	0.938**	0.928**	-	0.936**	0.905**

^a * and ** = significance at P = 0.05 and P = 0.01, respectively. Values followed by the same letter in a column do not differ significantly. ^b PU was applied as split applications (50% at transplanting, 25% at tillering, and 25% at panicle initiation); USG was applied at 29 kg N/ha at 10.12 cm depth; S = *Sesbania aculeata* grown in situ for 55 d; + N content of 0.49% in 1987-88, 0.51% in 1988-89, and 0.51% in 1989-90.

Table 2. Grain yield and N uptake (grain + straw) of residual wheat, nitrate production at wheat planting, and available soil N at the end of the experiment ^a. Pantnagar, U. P., India. 1987-90.

Treatment ^b	Grain yield (t/ha)			N uptake (kg/ha)		
	1987-88	1988-89	1989-90	1987-88	1988-89	1988-90
Control	0.9 a	1.0 a	1.2 a	23.5 a	29.8 a	28.3 a
PU @ 40 kg N	0.9 a	1.0 a	1.2 a	25.4 ab	31.4 ab	28.9 a
PU @ 80 kg N	0.9 a	1.0 a	1.3 a	27.5 abc	30.2 a	31.7 a
PU @ 120 kg N	0.9 a	1.1 a	1.2 a	30.2 bcd	31.7 ab	32.1 a
S + USG 1 WT	1.2 b	1.9 b	1.9 b	34.5 d	37.5 bc	42.1 b
S + USG 2 WT	1.2 b	1.7 b	1.9 b	27.5 abc	43.6 c	48.1 b
S + USG 3 WT	1.2 b	1.6 b	1.7 b	33.2 d	39.5 c	45.1 b
S + USG 4 WT	1.2 b	1.7 b	1.8 b	29.8 bcd	43.5 c	47.2 b
S + USG 5 WT	1.0 b	1.9 b	1.8 b	29.5 bcd	39.5 c	46.1 b
CD at 5%	0.29	0.34	0.41	5.41	6.12	7.30
<i>r</i> to nitrate production at wheat planting in respective years	0.921**	0.964**	0.960**	0.738**	0.920**	0.943**
	Nitrate N			Available soil N (kg/ha) (1990)		
	1987-88	1988-89	1989-90			
Control	14.2	17.1	12.8	264		
PU @ 40 kg N	14.9	16.1	13.4	270		
PU @ 80 kg N	15.7	19.1	13.0	270		
PU @ 120 kg N	14.9	20.1	14.1	283		
S + USG 1 WT	23.4	27.6	24.8	295		
S + USG 2 WT	20.8	29.3	22.5	293		
S + USG 3 WT	20.1	26.5	23.1	301		
S + USG 4 WT	22.5	27.2	25.7	286		
S + USG 5 WT	20.1	29.1	25.1	298		
Mean	18.51	23.57	19.38	284.4		

^a ** = significant at P = 0.01, ^b All treatments were applied to the rice crop only. Nitrate N and available soil N were determined for each treatment from combined sample of three replications.

after transplanting (WT) gave about the same yield as that of 120 kg N/ha applied as PU. Yields obtained with 120 kg N/ha as PU and Sesbania + USG@ 2-5 WT were significantly more than those with 80 kg N/ha as PU. Yield obtained with Sesbania + USG@ 1 WT was equal to that with 80 kg N/ha through PU. Grain yields had significant positive correlations with panicle number and with soil ammonium N measured during 1988-89 and 1989-90 at different rice growth stages (Table 1). N uptake by rice showed a trend similar to that of yield obtained.

Integrated management of Sesbania + USG@ 1-5 WT in lowland rice resulted in a significant increase in residual wheat yields compared with the control and with PU applied to rice at 40, 80, or 120 kg N/ha (Table 2). Increase in yield was greater in the second year and N uptake by the residual wheat crop was greater in the third year, and were significantly correlated with soil nitrate at wheat planting. Integrated GM + USG in rice - wheat rotation helped to maintain higher available soil N after 3 yr compared with the control and with PU application to the rice crop (Table 2).

Integrated N management with Sesbania GM and USG@ 2-4 WT can be used instead of PU at the recommended dose in a rice - wheat rotation where there is only time enough to grow a Sesbania crop for 50-60 d before transplanting rice. Using a renewable N source in lowland rice also benefits the succeeding wheat crop in a rice - wheat rotation, is equivalent to 20-30 kg N/ha, and will help to sustain soil N fertility. ■

Effects of gypsum, farmyard manure, and N on ameliorating highly sodic soil and on yields of rice and wheat

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We explored the possibility of reducing the dose of gypsum application in conjunction with applying farmyard manure (FYM) and at two N levels. The field experiment was conducted from